

CLASSIFICATION OF EDUCATION METHODS, TOOLS AND CONDITIONS FOR THEIR SELECTION IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. This article provides information on the classification of educational methods and tools in primary classes and the conditions for their selection.

Key words. Methods of education, content of education, pedagogical requirements, student, education time, discipline, means of education, teaching, direct requirements, new methods.

The method of education (from the Greek "methodos" - the way) is the way to achieve the goal of education. When applied to school practice, methods are methods of influencing the mind, will, feelings and behavior of students.

No educator is capable of creating completely new methods of education. The problem of improving the methods is always present, each educator solves it according to his ability, enriches the general methodology based on the expression of his private views in accordance with the specific conditions of the educational process. Such private improvement of educational methods is called educational methods. Educational methods are a part of the general method, a separate action, further definition. Figuratively speaking, methods are an unexplored path that a teacher paves the way with his students in order to achieve the set goal faster. If other educators start to use it, then gradually the methods can turn into broad-based ways - methods. Knowing the methods and methods of education, mastering the ability to use them correctly is one of the important characteristics that determine the level of pedagogical skills. That is the relevance of educational methods and methods.

In practice, the concept of educational tools is also distinguished. Methods mean a unit of influence, and a tool means a set of methods. A tool is neither a method nor a method. For example, work is a means of education, but showing it, evaluating work, showing mistakes in work are methods. Words (in a broad sense) are educational tools, but analogies are methods. In this connection, educational methods are sometimes defined as a system of methods and tools used for the successful implementation of a set goal. Also, methods and tools will definitely be present in the structure of the method.

Classification of educational methods. In modern pedagogy, there are dozens of classifications of education, some of which focus on solving practical tasks, and some reflect only theoretical tasks.

Methods are divided into persuasion, training, encouragement and reprimand according to their specific character. In this case, the general characteristic of the method reflects its orientation, originality, applicability. The general methods of education, which are distinguished by the more generalization of the methods, are firmly connected to this classification. It includes methods of persuasion, organization of activities, motivation of students' behavior. I.S. In Marenko's classification, groups of educational methods are named as follows: explanatory-reproductive, problem-based, teaching and training methods, stimulating, hindering, management, self-education.

Methods can be divided into two groups according to the results of their impact on students:

1. Ethical standards that influence the formation of motives, the formation of imagination, understanding, and ideas.
2. Affecting the formation of habits that determine one or another type of behavior.

Methods depend on the purpose and content of education. The methods of education are aimed at forming the qualities of a well-rounded person. Therefore,

taking into account the level of development of students is an important condition for the effective use of educational methods.

Pupils react differently to this or that educational influence. It depends on their special characteristics, the level of upbringing, the extent to which educational methods are chosen appropriately and effectively, and how skillfully they are used. The correct choice of educational methods helps to increase the activity of self-education of students in solving educational tasks positively. For example, in the process of working with first-grade students, the teacher uses the method of explaining to them the rules of behavior of students, the importance of having a clear agenda, and the need for students to follow a strict order when teaching students new work activities. In addition to explaining, he trains them to enter the classroom correctly, to greet the teacher and students, and to maintain discipline. At the same time, the students of the first grade are used to the above processes during the lesson. In this process, the positive work they have done, the results of their educational work, require encouragement. It can be seen that the teacher uses different methods and methods when conducting the educational process with students. The variety of educational methods shows the need to divide and classify them into types. Therefore, they can be divided into groups, taking into account their special characteristics. Every teacher (educator) who wants to achieve educational results should thoroughly master educational methods and their essence.

The task of the first group of methods is to create an understanding and knowledge of the social consciousness of the student about the rules and norms of life, ethics, labor relations. In the process of education, these rules and norms become the beliefs, confidence and life views of a person. This group includes spiritual, moral, aesthetic, ideological, legal, physical, ecological, economic, etc. content conversations and modeling techniques can be included.

With the help of the methods of the second group, the student forms habits related to spiritual content. The behavior of the student is formed in accordance with

the content of social education on the basis of moral habits and on the ground of activity.

Activity is an important resource that enriches the experience of social relations and social behavior of students. Among the methods of the second group, the method of pedagogical demand is important. Pedagogical demand can be the fulfillment of various tasks, i.e. expressing the norms of social behavior, performing a specific task that needs to be performed by participating in this or that activity, and encouraging one or another action.

Claims can be made directly or indirectly. Direct requirements are in the form of a strict command or instruction, a task, a guiding description. Indirect demands are expressed in the form of advice, request, rebuke, interest in activities, with the aim of arousing a sense of experience and aspiration. Requirements imply that the student has some level of awareness, reason, purpose, and belief. At the same time, the teacher must pay special attention to the standards of the requirements imposed on the students.

In the process of useful activities and specially organized tasks, positive behavior and characters are taught.

Teaching is an activity that motivates students to perform various actions and organized practical activities in a planned and systematic manner in order to transform social behavior into a normal form.

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